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Deliverable D5

Validation report on the traceability of voltage reference measuring systems, up to 36 kV for AC and 50 kV for DC, with superimposed frequency components up to 150 kHz including

- a) description of the chosen/developed voltage divider,
- b) the upgrade of the comparators,
- c) the characterisation and the traceability of the whole reference voltage measurement system,
- d) the uncertainty evaluation

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Glossary

AC	Alternating Current
DC	Direct Current
MV	Medium Voltage
EPM	European Partnership on Metrology
NMIs	National Metrology Institutes
VT	Voltage Transformer
DUT	Device Under Test
AWG	Arbitrary Waveform Generator
DAQ	Data Acquisition System / Module
UD	Universal Divider
HF	High Frequency
HV	High Voltage
RMS	Root Mean Square
RC	Resistor-Capacitor (circuit or divider)
LNE	Laboratoire National de Métrologie et d'Essais (France)
FFII	Fundación para la Investigación y el Desarrollo de la Industria (Spain)
INRIM	Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (Italy)
RISE	Research Institutes of Sweden
UNICAMPANIA	University of Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli" (Italy)
VSL	VSL Dutch Metrology Institute (Netherlands)
MSO	Mixed Signal Oscilloscope
PFG	Power Frequency Generator
RCVD	Resistive-Capacitive Voltage Divider
SF	Scale Factor
SFS	Sinusoidal Frequency Sweep
PXI	PCI eXtensions for Instrumentation
PLL	Phase Locked Loop
LFRD	Low Frequency Reference Device
HFRD	High Frequency Reference Device
LVD	Low Voltage Divider
LFA	Low Frequency Amplifier
HFA	High Frequency Amplifier
HFVT	High-Frequency Voltage Transformer

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1 Summary

This validation report focuses on the development and characterization of advanced voltage measurement system for the testing of medium-voltage instrument transformers under supraharmonic conditions. The work addresses the need for accurate and traceable measurements beyond the fundamental 50/60 Hz, covering the 9 kHz to 150 kHz range and reaching voltage levels up to 50 kV DC and 36 kV AC.

Several measuring systems have been designed and validated, each offering specific advantages. Lower voltage solutions provide higher accuracy and lower uncertainties. Increasing the voltage introduces additional uncertainty sources and lower accuracy.

Together, these solutions establish a versatile test infrastructure for calibration and performance assessment of instrument transformers, supporting both metrological research and future standardization in the field of power quality and high-frequency phenomena.

2 Introduction

One of the most urgent needs in power quality control of medium voltage instruments is to develop advanced measuring systems for AC and DC high voltage waveforms with superimposed frequency components representative of real-world grid disturbances [1–3]. These are needed to properly evaluate voltage transformers under realistic operating conditions, especially those installed in medium voltage networks where harmonic disturbances in the 9 kHz–150 kHz band are increasingly present. Even among leading National Metrology Institutes (NMIs), most reference measuring systems remain restricted to frequencies below 9 kHz [4]. Similarly, commercial digital recorders available on the market often fall short of the performance requirements necessary for precise VT characterisation.

As a result, validated and stable measuring systems have become a critical component of modern test setups. The ability to measure realistic AC and DC voltage waveforms with proper spectral analysis up to 150 kHz is indispensable for the evaluation of voltage-dependent devices, such as VTs, insulators, and other power system components, under high frequency disturbances.

The ADMIT project [5] addresses this technological gap by developing and validating several complementary measurement system architectures:

- Chapter 3 - LNE up to 50 kV and 150 kHz
- Chapter 4 - RISE up to 50 kV and 150 kHz
- Chapter 5 - VTT up to 100 kV and 100 kHz
- Chapter 6 - INRIM up to 45 kV and 1000 kHz
- Chapter 7 - FFII up to 35 kV and 150 kHz
- Chapter 8 - UniCampania up to 3 kV and 150 kHz

Together, these systems enable the traceability of AC voltages up to 36 kV, DC voltages up to 50 kV, and proper analysis of superimposed components with amplitudes in the 9 kHz to 150 kHz range. This represents a significant step forward, empowering NMIs to provide new calibration capabilities and extending traceability into a frequency range of growing importance for modern electrical networks.

3 LNE measuring system

3.1 Introduction

This section describes the development and characterization of a reference high voltage system developed at LNE, intended for instrument transformer calibration up to 150 kHz, in accordance with IEC 61869, for measurements involving a 35 kV fundamental component with superimposed harmonics typically ranging from a few volts up to several hundreds of volts.

The objective of this work is to develop a reference measurement chain capable of accurately calibrating and assessing the conformity of instrument transformers (ITs) according to the wideband accuracy classes defined in IEC 61869, particularly WB2 and WB3, including the measurement of low-amplitude harmonics in the supraharmonic range. Most existing approaches do not specifically address these requirements and remain limited in their ability to measure harmonics with very low amplitudes. In practice, supraharmonic components are several orders of magnitude lower than the fundamental, requiring measurement systems with very high dynamic ranges. Meeting standard limits for weak harmonics, down to 0.1 % or even 0.01 % of the fundamental, demands reference systems capable of resolving these components without distortion or coupling from the fundamental signal. Current methods either rely on simplified frequency-response measurements at low amplitudes or on combined fundamental–harmonic approaches, typically limited to lower frequencies and relatively high harmonic levels (e.g., ≥ 1 %). A reference method extending up to 150 kHz, particularly for voltage transformers, is still lacking, which remains a key limitation for reliable conformity assessment in the supraharmonic range. To address this gap, this work proposes a new reference chain developed within the ADMIT project. It enables conformity assessment of ITs up to Class WB3, as defined in IEC 61869. Achieving the required uncertainty levels—at least five times lower than the standard limits—requires a redesigned measurement architecture, including a voltage divider with flat amplitude and phase response, as well as dedicated attenuators, filters and acquisition systems.

The developed system is composed of a high voltage divider, precision attenuators and high pass filters, all specifically designed and characterized for this application. It incorporates two parallel measurement paths. The first path, based on the high voltage divider combined with an attenuator, is optimized for measurements of the fundamental component with superimposed harmonics. The second path, consisting of the high voltage divider followed by a high pass filter, is dedicated to the measurement of very low-level harmonic components by improving the signal to noise ratio. Both paths are connected to a digitizer, forming a complete and modular measurement system. The expanded measurement uncertainty has been carefully evaluated and demonstrates that the system is suitable for instrument transformer calibration up to 150 kHz. Furthermore, the architecture of the system allows for future extension up to 500 kHz, addressing emerging needs related to high frequency power quality disturbances and enhancing measurement capabilities in this domain.

3.2 Calibration of Voltage Transformers up to 150 kHz

The calibration methodology described in this section establishes the reference chain for assessing voltage transformers in the extended frequency range up to 150 kHz. It provides the practical implementation of the proposed approach. This section first presents the general and theoretical principles of calibration, then details the adopted chain architecture, followed by the design and characterization of its key components and finally the uncertainties of measurement.

3.2.1 Calibration Principle

The amplitude and phase assessment of ITs is performed using a reference IT in combination with a digitizer, as illustrated in Figure 1. The ITs are used to scale down the high voltage to levels compatible with the digitizer input. The reference IT consists of impedances $Z1$ and $Z2$ with known characteristics, defined by $N1(n)$ and $\varphi1(n)$, where n is the harmonic order, $N1(n)$ corresponds to the amplitude transfer function (scale factor), and $\varphi1(n)$ represents the phase response. The IT under test is modelled by impedances $Z3$ and $Z4$, with unknown characteristics $N2(n)$ and $\varphi2(n)$, corresponding respectively to its scale factor and phase response.

Figure 1. Calibration of an instrument transformer by comparison to a reference high-voltage chain and a digitizer.

The outputs of both ITs are connected to a digitizer, which acquires $V1(n)$ and $V2(n)$. The frequency dependent scale factor of the IT under calibration is determined using Equation (1), while the phase response is obtained using Equation (2).

$$N2(n) = N1(n) \cdot \frac{V1(n)}{V2(n)} = N1(n) \cdot N3(n) \tag{1}$$

$$\phi2(n) = \phi1(n) + \Delta\phi(n) \tag{2}$$

The calibration of the IT relies on the accurate knowledge of the scale factor and phase response of the reference IT as well as on the precise measurement of the voltage ratio and phase difference between the output signals at the digitizer. Consequently, the traceability and overall uncertainty of the calibration are primarily determined by the performance of the reference IT and the digitizer.

3.2.2 The generator

The generation architecture used here consists of the parallel connection between the Power Frequency (at 50/60 Hz) generator and the High-Frequency generator. It proposes a classical characterization method based on the comparison of the outputs of a reference VT and of a VT under test, by means of a comparator. Both the comparator as well as the reference VT should have sufficient accuracy in the frequency range from the power frequency up to 150 kHz.

The Power Frequency Generator is obtained by means of an Arbitrary Waveform Generator cascaded by a low-voltage amplifier, cascaded, in turns, by a step-up transformer to reach the required voltage levels. Instead, the high-frequency generator is obtained by means of a second Arbitrary Waveform Generator cascaded by another low-voltage amplifier, having an output frequency range from DC up to 150 kHz. The generation measurement setup is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Setup implementation of the generator

The applied voltage signals are provided by a two-channels arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) Keysight 33612A (± 10 V output range, 660 MHz maximum sampling rate, and 64 million of samples per channel of onboard memory). The output of the first channel of the AWG (AWG ch. 1) is connected to a voltage amplifier (± 120 V, ± 50 A, 6 kVA) feeding the VT under test through a 100 V / 35 kV with a power capacity of 5 kVA. The output of the second AWG (AWG ch. 2) is connected to a power amplifier N4L LPA400 (± 400 V, 50 mA, DC – 1 MHz, selectable gain). The device under test (DUT) represents the total load of the whole system (mainly reference IT and IT under calibration). Two other dividers have been used to measure 50 Hz and high frequency voltages respectively, just at the output of the corresponding generators. Divider D1 is a commercial RC divider (300 M Ω /10 pF, ratio 1000:1, accuracy 0.1 % at 50 Hz and 1 % at 150 kHz). Divider D2 is a commercial RC divider (100 M Ω /3 pF, ratio 1000:1, accuracy 0.1 % at 50 Hz and 1 % at 150 kHz).

A full remote control of the setup has been implemented in LabVIEW environment. The realized software allows to choose generation parameters, to enable and disable the generation, and to monitor overvoltage and overcurrent situations.

3.3 Development of the reference IT

3.3.1 Reference IT principle

The reference IT acts as a calibrated divider front end that converts high-voltage signals into measurable low-voltage quantities with preserved amplitude and phase information. It should be capable of operating under both DC and AC conditions depending on the type of the IT. For DC applications, test voltages can reach up to 50 kV and measurements are typically performed at 100 % of the rated voltage. For AC applications, the reference condition is usually a 50 Hz (or 60 Hz) sinusoidal waveform with a test voltage of around 35 kV rms (50 kV peak), also applied at nominal voltage. Harmonic components are intentionally superimposed on the fundamental waveform. These harmonics can have amplitudes ranging from 0.01 % to 1 % of the fundamental voltage. The key challenge lies in accurately detecting and quantifying such small harmonic components, both in amplitude and phase, when they are superimposed on a large fundamental voltage. This becomes even more demanding when the frequency of the harmonic content extends up to 150 kHz. The chain must therefore ensure excellent linearity, high dynamic range and minimal phase error across a wide bandwidth.

To address this, two main measurement approaches can be considered. The first technique involves using a single high-voltage divider (HVD) connected to a digitizer with a very high dynamic range. This allows the chain to simultaneously capture both the high-amplitude fundamental component and the much smaller harmonic components. The main advantage of this approach is that it preserves the full waveform and avoids the need for any signal conditioning. However, the drawback lies in the difficulty of finding digitizers or acquisition chains that offer sufficiently high resolution, linearity and noise performance to resolve very-low-level signals (e.g., 0.01 % of the fundamental).

The second approach consists of applying filtering techniques to suppress the fundamental frequency and retain only the harmonic components. This can significantly reduce the dynamic range requirement of the acquisition chain, as the large fundamental component is no longer present in the captured signal. However, this method introduces its own challenges. The accuracy of the measurement can be affected by the non-linearity and imperfections of the filter, particularly in terms of amplitude flatness and phase response.

Each technique has its own advantages and limitations and the choice between them depends on the specific performance targets and available instrumentation. In our case, the target is to be able to assess Class 0.1-WB3 ITs with a target uncertainty five times lower than the accuracy limits defined in IEC 61869-1, namely, 0.02 % for the fundamental frequency, 0.2 % up to 20 kHz and 1 % up to 150 kHz. To overcome the limitations of each individual technique, we have adopted a dual-path architecture that implements both approaches, enabling redundancy, flexibility and improved reliability in harmonic measurements. This hybrid strategy allows for cross-verification. The implemented chain is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Overview schematic of the reference IT for instrument transformer calibration up to 150 kHz.

The reference IT begins with the HVD composed of resistive and capacitive elements (RC structure). The scale factor of the divider has been chosen to be 500. This scaling ensures that the harmonic signal remains high enough for the filtration operation. On the other hand, the fundamental component, after division, reaches a level of ± 100 V peak at the output of the HVD. To bring this signal within the input range of most digitizers, an attenuation stage is developed to reduce the signal to ± 1 V peak, compatible with both the input range and linearity specifications of most high-performance digitizers.

The selection between Path 1 and Path 2 is based on the signal amplitude at the digitizer input. Path 1 (HVD + attenuator) is used whenever the expected input signal is higher than approximately 1 mV (this limitation is defined according to the characterization results of the selected digitizer, see below), which guarantees an adequate signal-to-noise ratio. Otherwise, Path 2 (HVD + high-pass filter) is employed to enhance sensitivity. As an illustration, for a fundamental of 50 kV, a harmonic at 0.1 % of the fundamental corresponds to 50 V at the primary and about 1 mV at the digitizer input after division (scale factor 50,000), making Path 1 appropriate. However, for lower fundamental voltages, the same harmonic ratio results in signals below 1 mV, and Path 2 must therefore be used. This criterion ensures robust operation across different primary voltage levels.

3.3.2 Design of the HVD

The voltage divider is the primary sensing element that scales down the voltage. The development of a new voltage divider is necessary to overcome the limitations of currently available commercial dividers and existing in-house solutions. Most of these dividers are specifically designed for DC, AC@50–60 Hz or impulse voltage measurements and are not optimized for broadband applications involving harmonic content up to 150 kHz. They often feature large scale factors (e.g., 10,000), which limit the output signal amplitude and reduce the visibility of low-level harmonic components, especially when their amplitude represents very small fraction of the fundamental waveform. In addition, these dividers typically suffer from higher noise-to-signal ratios and limited or non-linear frequency responses, making them unsuitable for precise amplitude and phase characterization of weak harmonic signals superimposed on the fundamental.

We have decided to choose an RC structure which combines resistive and capacitive branches in parallel and which, with proper compensation, can reach a bandwidth of several MHz. The high-voltage arm consists of a resistor of $R1 = 100$ M Ω and a capacitor of $C1 = 100$ pF. Moreover, to maintain waveform fidelity, the time constant of the low-voltage part (comprising $R2$, $C2$, $R3$ and $C3$, as well as the downstream attenuator components $R4$, $R5$, $C4$ and $C5$) has been precisely adjusted to match the time constant of the high-voltage arm ($R1$, $C1$). This compensation ensures that the divider maintains a flat frequency response and minimal phase shift across the operating bandwidth.

Figure 4. The developed RC high-voltage divider for voltages up to 50 kV peak: (a) high-voltage arm using NP0 capacitors and metallic resistors on a PCB with a zigzag structure; two PCBs mounted in parallel and in opposite directions to reduce electric field influence. (b) Low-voltage arm with a compact coaxial structure, using the same SMD components as the high-voltage arm; (c) electrical circuit of the low-voltage arm.

The HVD that was developed is shown in Figure 4. To build the resistor R1, we have selected resistors of $1\text{ M}\Omega \pm 0.1\%$ from Vishay, type MELF (metal electrode leadless face), 400 mW, 350 V and 15 ppm/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$, due to their excellent voltage linearity. We have measured their voltage linearity from 10 V to 350 V, and they exhibited very good performance, with a voltage deviation better than 0.005 %. When the rated voltage was applied continuously for 10 min, the resistors showed minimal self-heating effects with a deviation better than 0.001 %, confirming excellent thermal stability under power dissipation. We have developed a 50 kV (+20 % of safety margin) section by assembling 200 resistors in series using a zigzag structure on a printed circuit board (PCB). Despite the excellent characteristics of each individual component, applying high voltage has generated intense electric fields around the resistors which have affected the voltage linearity by 0.1 %. To mitigate the influence of these electric fields, we have decided to use two PCBs placed in parallel and opposite directions, so the current flowing through one board circulates in the opposite direction of the second one. This configuration significantly improves the overall voltage linearity. The value of R1 in this case is about 100 M Ω (two 200 M Ω in parallel) and the DC current at the rated voltage is equal to 0.5 mA at 50 kV, which is high enough to eliminate the influence of the leakage current.

To build the capacitor C1, only one type of capacitor meets our requirements: negative/positive-zero (NP0) ceramic capacitors, known for their very low temperature coefficient (TC), typically less than 30 ppm/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Polypropylene capacitors also offer good performance but their higher TC (e.g., <300 ppm/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$) exceeds the target uncertainty of 0.02 % at the fundamental frequency. The value of C1 has been selected to be 100 pF to minimize the influence of parasitic capacitance to ground and to limit power dissipation from the voltage source. Murata capacitors rated at 10 nF and 650 V peak-to-peak have been chosen. Each capacitor has been soldered in parallel with each MELF resistor.

In the low-voltage arm of the HVD, the same component technologies as those used in the high-voltage arm have been employed. This approach helps cancel out mutual influences such as temperature, voltage and frequency behaviours. Moreover, the low-voltage arm has been designed with a compact layout to better meet these conditions and minimize parasitic effects. The components R2 and C2 have been soldered in a coaxial configuration to eliminate the influence of stray capacitance to ground. R3 is a damping resistor, and its value is equal to the characteristic impedance of the coaxial cable (50 Ω).

The HVD has been calibrated under various conditions to characterize its scale factor and dynamic behaviour. The main results are presented in Table 1, and the output of the divider has been loaded using a measuring instrument with an input impedance equivalent to that of the attenuator (see section 3.3.3).

Table 1. Calibration results of the HVD.

Condition	Voltage Range	Scale Factor	Relative Deviation	Remarks
DC	1 kV to 50 kV	500.848	0.004 %	Voltage response
AC/50 Hz	1 kV to 35 kV rms	500.729	0.011 %	Voltage response
DC to 150 kHz	200 V	500.37	0.07 %	Frequency response
Phase shift	200 V			Time constant = -38 ns

At AC@50 Hz, the divider was calibrated from 1 kV to 50 kV yielding a scale factor of 500.848 with a relative deviation of 0.004 %. A second calibration at AC@50 Hz, from 1 kV to 35 kV rms, produced a scale factor of 500.729 with a deviation of 0.011 %. Additionally, a frequency sweep from DC to 150 kHz was performed at 200 V, resulting in a scale factor of 500.37 with a maximum deviation of 0.10 %. Regarding phase behavior, a time constant of -38 ns was measured, characterizing the phase shift performance of the divider across frequency, and can be calculated using Equation (3):

$$\text{Phase (rad)} = 2\pi ft, \quad (3)$$

where f is the frequency of the signal and t is the time constant.

The calibration results demonstrate that the HVD offers excellent performance in terms of accuracy and stability across a wide range of voltages and frequencies. The divider meets the stringent accuracy requirement in terms of the scale factor from DC to 150 kHz. Additionally, the measured time constant of -38 ns ensures reliable correction of the phase behaviour for each frequency.

3.3.3 Design of the Attenuator

The attenuator plays a crucial role in the measurement chain by further reducing the already scaled-down voltage from the HVD to a level compatible with the input range of the measurement instrument such as a digitizer. Beyond voltage reduction, the attenuator also aids in impedance matching between the divider and the measuring device, minimizing signal reflections and preserving measurement accuracy. By providing a stable and linear attenuation over a wide frequency range, it helps maintain signal integrity. The input impedance of the attenuator is designed to emulate the input impedance of the digitizer; therefore, when the attenuator is connected, HVD frequency behaviour does not change if compared to the behaviour measured with HVD only. As, for the case at hand, the input impedance of the digitizer is typically about 1 M Ω /30 pF, while the input impedance of the attenuator is fixed to R4 \cong 1 M Ω and C4 \cong 30 pF.

The developed attenuator has a scale factor of 100. It is built using components similar to the HVD (NPO capacitors and metallic resistors) and features a coaxial and compact structure in order to minimize parasitic effects and maintain excellent high-frequency behaviour. The output of the attenuator is matched to the input impedance of the digitizer, typically also equal to 1 M Ω in parallel with 30 pF. Additionally, the time constant of the high-voltage part is matched with that of the low-voltage part to ensure good frequency behaviour.

The combination of the HVD and the attenuator results in a total scale factor of 50,000. Consequently, when measuring a high-voltage signal of 50 kV peak, the chain provides an output of 1 V, which can be accurately captured using the 1 V input range of the digitizer. Two attenuators have been developed: attenuator A is associated with the HVD, while attenuator B is potentially associated with the instrument transformer (IT) under calibration. Additional attenuators can be easily developed to match the scale factors of various ITs (e.g., attenuation of 5, 10, 50 and 200) or various impedances (e.g., 2 M Ω and 10 M Ω). The electrical circuit and the developed attenuators are shown in Figure 5.

(b)

(c)

Figure 5. Developed attenuators. (a) Electrical circuit; (b) measurement results for amplitude response; (c) measurement results for phase response.

From the results, it is shown that the frequency responses of both attenuators are relatively flat over the range from DC to 150 kHz. Attenuator A maintains a scale factor around 102.5, with minimal variation (~0.1 %). Attenuator B shows slightly more variation, with a gradual decrease in the scale factor from approximately 102.6 to 102.3, which re-mains negligible. In terms of phase, the phase at the fundamental frequency is almost zero for both attenuators. A small overshoot is observed around 7 kHz; beyond that, the phase response is nearly linear, allowing for correction if necessary. Note that the scale factor and phase values are obtained under certain conditions; the load, specifically the input impedance of the digitizer, has a significant influence. For example, a 1 pF variation in the capacitance and 1 % variation in the resistance of 1 MΩ affects the scale factor by about 0.01 % and the phase by approximately 0.0015 crad. Therefore, the input impedance of the digitizer must be measured precisely to apply corrections if necessary.

3.3.4 Design of the Filter

The filter enhances the sensing capability for weak harmonics. The objective of the filter is to analyse high frequency harmonic components with very small amplitudes (e.g., 0.01 % of the fundamental). It is required to strongly attenuate the fundamental frequency (50 Hz) and its low-order harmonics, particularly up to a few hundreds of Hz. The goal is to suppress dominant low-frequency components and only retain harmonics in the range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. To achieve sufficient rejection of the fundamental and its harmonics, a filter of at least the 4th order is necessary. The use of filters in harmonic measurement is common and has been the subject of numerous scientific studies; we have decided to develop a high-pass filter (HPF) to analyse these supraharmonics.

The equivalent impedance of the filter needs to be high to not strongly disturb the metrological characteristics of the HVD. However, this high impedance comes with trade-offs: it tends to increase the cutoff frequency of the filter. In addition, the capacitor C6 of the filter needs to be much higher than the input capacitance of the digitizer (typically around 30 pF), because together they form a capacitive voltage divider. If the filter capacitor is too small, it will significantly reduce the signal reaching the digitizer, resulting in undesired attenuation of the output voltage. As a result, an ideal filter response is not achievable, and a balance must be found between attenuation performance and phase linearity; a small attenuation and phase shift will still be present in the range of 9 kHz–150 kHz.

Another limitation in the filter design arises from the input resistor of the digitizer, typically 1 MΩ, which is internally connected in parallel with its input capacitance. This resistor cannot be removed or modified, yet it forms part of the overall RC network seen by the filter. As a result, it introduces a fixed time constant that limits the ability to precisely control the cutoff frequency of the filter using the external resistor R7 alone. Even if R7 is carefully selected, the presence of the digitizer’s internal 1 MΩ resistor means that the effective resistance seen by the filter is not purely defined by R7, but by the parallel combination of R7 and the digitizer’s input resistance. This constraint reduces the flexibility in filter tuning and must be considered when designing the frequency response. In particular, it makes it more difficult to achieve sharp cutoffs or target specific bandwidths without compromising other aspects such as signal attenuation or phase linearity. A possible solution is to develop impedance matchers or active filters, but such developments will bring other difficulties such as electronic noise.

For these reasons, the filter is intended to be used only when the harmonic voltages are very low (typically < 0.1 % of the fundamental), where precise filtering is critical. In cases where harmonics are more significant, the primary measurement chain (HVD + attenuator) is used without the filter to preserve accuracy. Because the implementation of the filter slightly modifies the electrical behaviour of the measurement chain, particularly in terms of impedance, frequency response and phase behaviour, it is essential to characterize the complete chain with the filter to ensure measurement reliability and traceability.

We have chosen to set up a 4th-order low-pass filter using a cascade of RC (resistor–capacitor) stages. A 4th-order passive RC filter was selected to ensure stability, simplicity and reproducibility in the 9–150 kHz frequency range. Passive filters present the advantage of being inherently linear and free from additional noise or distortion that can be introduced by active components. A higher-order design was considered unnecessary as the 4th-order response already provided sufficient attenuation outside the band of interest while maintaining good phase characteristics. Each stage consisted of a 220-pF capacitor and a 500-kΩ resistor to ground, forming individual first-order low-pass filters. By cascading these stages, we obtained a sharper frequency roll-off characteristic of a 4th-order filter, which attenuates low-frequency components more aggressively. The capacitors and resistors were chosen from the same technologies as the HVD and the attenuator. The results of this filter are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The developed filter: (a) electrical circuit; (b) gain and frequency results of the developed filter only; (c) gain and frequency results of the developed filter associated with the HVD.

From the results of the filter alone, it can be observed that the attenuation between 9 kHz and 150 kHz is approximately 5 dB. This attenuation is primarily due to the influence of the input impedance of the digitizer, as previously discussed. The 50 Hz fundamental component is attenuated by about 85 dB, while the 10th harmonic of the 50 Hz signal (i.e., 500 Hz) is attenuated by approximately 40 dB. When the filter is combined with the HVD, the attenuation between 9 kHz and 150 kHz increases significantly, ranging from 60 dB to 57 dB, and the 50 Hz fundamental is attenuated by approximately 126 dB. These results demonstrate that the filter is sufficiently effective in suppressing both the fundamental and low-frequency harmonics. However, as previously noted, the impedance seen by the filter (e.g., impedance of the digitizer) has a strong influence on the gain and phase responses of the filter. According to the characterization results, a variation of just 1 pF in this impedance can lead to an error of approximately 0.9 % in gain and 0.04 crad in phase at 150 kHz.

In practice, the divider and associated filter are calibrated together as a complete chain to ensure traceability of the scale factor and frequency response in the 9–150 kHz range. Since the calibration is performed with an impedance slightly different from that of the digitizer input, a correction is applied during data processing to account for the exact input impedance of the digitizer. This guarantees that the influence of the filter and the impedance mismatch are both compensated for, ensuring accurate amplitude and phase measurements over the frequency range of interest.

3.3.5 Selection and Characterization of the Digitizer

The digitizer completes the sensing chain by converting the conditioned analogue signals into digital data for further analysis. To ensure accurate measurements, the digitizer used in the chain must meet several important requirements. Its input impedance, typically 1 M Ω /30 pF, needs to be known accurately in order to correct the measuring chains if needed in terms of both scale factor and phase. When used in combination with the filter, the digitizer characteristics become even more critical. In this configuration, the digitizer and filter together form a capacitive voltage divider, which can significantly affect the signal amplitude if not properly accounted for. Therefore, the input capacitance of the digitizer must be precisely known and considered during chain calibration. The corrections of the input impedances of the digitizers are usually obtained by experimentations.

The input voltage range must be compatible with the output of the measurement chain, ideally allowing a 1 V peak full-scale input when measuring up to 50 kV peak, assuming a total scale factor of 50,000. The digitizer should provide high resolution, preferably 16 bits or more, to accurately capture small signal components such as harmonics down to 0.1 % of the fundamental. A wide analogue bandwidth is also essential; the digitizer should offer a bandwidth of at least several MHz to accurately capture signal content up to 150 kHz without amplitude distortion or phase error. A high sampling rate (e.g., 10 MS/s or higher) is required to prevent aliasing and enable precise time- and frequency-domain analysis.

Several digitizers were considered for high-voltage measurements, including the PicoScope 4262, Fluke 8588A, Keysight 3458A, NI PXIe-6396 and Applicos WFD22. While the Fluke and Keysight models offer excellent accuracy and resolution for low-frequency metrology, their single inputs necessitate the need to use two digitizers with a high-accuracy synchronization chain. The NI PXIe-6396 and Applicos WFD22 provide higher performance and resolution but require more complex integration and software development. The PicoScope 4262 was ultimately chosen for its ideal balance of low noise (~ 8.5 μ V RMS), 16-bit resolution, 5 MHz bandwidth and 10 MS/s sampling rate, along with fast USB communication, easy programming and two internally synchronized channels. The datasheet of the PicoScope 4262 does not specify the time delay between the two channels. This delay has been determined during the calibration of the instrument. An alternative method to mitigate a possible delay is to interchange the oscilloscope channels so that the effect cancels out. However, we chose to include this delay directly in the measurement uncertainty in section 3.4. These features make it well suited for capturing small harmonic signals up to 150 kHz and for rapid integration.

The PicoScope 4262 was characterized in the ± 1 V range by measuring small signals of 10 mV and 1 mV amplitude, corresponding to 1 % and 0.1 % of the range, respectively. This was performed to assess the scope's ability to detect low-level signals within a high dynamic range in the frequency from 10 kHz to 150 kHz. The oscilloscope was configured identically to its operational setup for the acquisition of a fundamental @50 Hz and the superimposed harmonics: with a 5 MHz analogue bandwidth, 10 MS/s sampling rate and horizontal resolution set to 20 ms/div. Measurements were carried out using two methods: direct time-domain acquisition with RMS readings and frequency-domain analysis using FFT. While the RMS method provides a general measure of signal energy, it incorporates all harmonic components, along with noise, offset and spurious

signals, which reduces its accuracy, especially at low amplitudes around 0.1 % of the range. In contrast, the FFT method is more representative, as it allows for direct extraction of specific harmonic amplitudes, making it more suitable for evaluating small-signal detection. The results were expressed either in terms of absolute amplitude or as the ratio of amplitudes and their phase shifts between two input channels. This ratio is particularly relevant, as it reflects the actual quantity being measured in the chain according to the governing Equations (1) and (2). Using the amplitude ratio also helps reduce sensitivity to absolute gain variations or noise and thus provides a more accurate evaluation of the chain harmonic measurement performance. The results are presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Digitizer error across a range of frequencies (10 kHz to 150 kHz) for different measurement methods (rms and FFT) and signal amplitudes (1 mV and 10 mV) in ± 1 V range.

It is evident that RMS-based measurements, particularly for individual channels (A and B), exhibit higher errors, around 0.2 % at 10 mV. At the 1 mV level, the rms results are unusable due to the influence of noise, offset and non-harmonic components included in the rms calculation. The amplitude ratio (A/B) shows significantly lower and more stable errors, typically below 0.05 %, demonstrating improved accuracy in detecting small harmonic components. Even at very low signal levels (1 mV or 0.1 % of the range), the FFT method maintains acceptable performance, with errors remaining under 0.3 % across the frequency range. In terms of phase shift between both inputs, an error of approximately 0.1 crad is observed up to 150 kHz, measured by applying the same signal to both inputs. At the fundamental frequency (AC or DC), the FFT technique has also been used to measure the amplitude ratio (A/B), with observed errors around 0.04 % with an associated uncertainty of 0.01 %.

These results confirm that the PicoScope 4262, when used with FFT-based ratio measurements, provides a more accurate and representative evaluation of harmonic components in high-dynamic-range conditions, particularly when signal amplitudes are low. For harmonic voltages lower than 0.1 % of the range and down to 0.01 %, the use of the dedicated filter becomes beneficial. In this case, the filter enhances the harmonic component while suppressing the fundamental, so that the voltage applied to the digitizer remains above 1 mV, making it measurable with acceptable error levels, typically around 0.3 %, as demonstrated.

3.4 Estimation of Measurement Uncertainties

3.4.1 Measurement Procedure

Two measurement paths are available. The first path, consisting of the HVD followed by the attenuator (scale factor of 50,000), is used to measure the fundamental frequency and any harmonic components with amplitudes greater than 0.1 % of the fundamental. The maximum test voltage is 50 kV according to the characteristics of the HVD. In this case, 0.1 % of the fundamental corresponds to 50 V at the divider input, i.e., 1 mV at the measurement output. However, if the test voltage is lower than 50 kV, the relative criterion of 0.1 % is no longer meaningful. Therefore, there is a minimum limit of 1 mV at the output, regardless of the actual test voltage.

The second path, which bypasses the attenuator and uses the HPF, is configured to only measure harmonics with amplitudes as low as 0.01 % of the fundamental (or output voltage < 1 mV if using the first path). Since this path avoids additional attenuation, it offers a better signal-to-noise ratio for detecting weak harmonics that might otherwise be buried in the noise floor or undetectable due to limited resolution.

This separation of signal acquisition paths ensures the following:

- Path 1: (HVD + attenuator) for the measurement of fundamental and harmonic amplitudes as low as 0.1 % of the fundamental (or output voltage as low as 1 mV);
- Path 2: (HVD + HPF) for the measurement of weak harmonics as low as 0.01 % of the fundamental (or output voltage lower than 1 mV using the first path).

The calibration uncertainty depends solely on the calibration uncertainty of the reference measuring chain (Path 1 or Path 2) and on the voltage ratio measured at the digitizer side. The influence of temperature has been neglected, since all components used in the development have very small temperature coefficients, and all measurements are performed in a high-precision, temperature-controlled room at $(23 \pm 1) ^\circ\text{C}$.

3.4.2 Uncertainty Estimation for the Fundamental Component

The main uncertainty contributions for the measurement of the fundamental are as follows:

- Calibration of Path 1: To achieve low uncertainty at the fundamental, the entirety of Path 1 is calibrated using our internal reference procedure that accounts for stray impedance effects. Calibration is performed with an impedance equivalent to that of the digitizer. The resulting standard uncertainty is 0.0015 % for amplitude (AC and DC) and 0.0015 crad for phase.
- Digitizer calibration: The voltage ratio is calibrated in both amplitude and phase by injecting two known voltage signals directly into the digitizer inputs in the same configuration as it is used during high-voltage measurements. The signals are analysed using FFT to determine the complex ratio between channels. The estimated standard uncertainties are 0.01 % for amplitude (AC and DC) and 0.01 crad for phase (at 50 Hz).
- Influence of the attenuator load: The uncertainty caused by load effects is included in the overall uncertainty budget since Path 1 is calibrated without the digitizer. The input impedance of the digitizer needs to be accurately determined to correct this influence if needed. We consider an associated uncertainty of 1 pF for the capacitive part and 1 % for the resistive part, resulting in an estimated uncertainty of 0.01 % for amplitude (AC and DC) and approximately 0.0015 crad for phase, considered negligible.

3.4.3 Uncertainty Estimation of Harmonics using path 1.

To ensure accurate harmonic analysis from 9 kHz to 150 kHz, we set a threshold of 1 mV (output voltage > 1 mV if using Path 1). Harmonic components above this threshold are acquired using Path 1. To maintain the required measurement uncertainty, each component of Path 1 (HVD, attenuator) must be calibrated separately. Calibrating the entire path as a whole can degrade accuracy, especially for phase, due to the small voltage on the output of Path 1 (scale factor of 50,000). Calibrating each part independently under controlled conditions minimizes uncertainty and ensures traceability. The main contributions are as follows:

- HVD Calibration: Calibrated up to 150 kHz. From Table 1, a standard uncertainty of 0.1 % is adopted for amplitude. For phase, a correction factor of 38 ns is applied, with a standard uncertainty of 1 ns (equivalent to 0.1 crad at 150 kHz). The HVD is calibrated with a load equivalent to the attenuator (30 pF//1 M Ω).
- HVD Load Sensitivity: A variation of 1 pF in capacitance and 1 % in the 1 M Ω resistive load introduces a standard uncertainty of approximately 0.005 % for the amplitude and a negligible phase uncertainty over 9 kHz to 150 kHz.
- Attenuator Calibration: Calibrated up to 150 kHz in both amplitude and phase. From Figure 5, a standard uncertainty of 0.1 % is adopted for amplitude. For phase, a correction is applied, with a standard uncertainty of 0.1 crad.
- Attenuator Load Sensitivity: A 1 pF change in capacitance and 1 % variation in resistive load introduces an uncertainty of approximately 0.005 crad in phase and 0.03 % in gain over the 9 kHz to 150 kHz range.

- Digitizer Calibration: As shown in Figure 7, for harmonic voltages at 0.1 % of the fundamental, a standard uncertainty of 0.3 % can be adopted. For 1 % of the fundamental, 0.1 % uncertainty is applicable. The associated phase uncertainty is 0.1 crad.

3.4.4 Uncertainty Estimation of Harmonics using path 2

For accurate detection of very-low-level harmonics down to 0.01 % of the fundamental (or output voltage < 0.1 mV if using the path1), we use Path 2 (HVD + Filter). The output voltage of Path 2 is then higher than 1 mV due to its low attenuation (about 60 dB).

The uncertainty contributions come primarily from Path 2 and the digitizer.

- Path 2 Calibration: To achieve accurate results, Path 2 can be calibrated at 20 V, from 9 kHz to 150 kHz, using our reference procedure that accounts for stray impedance effects. Calibration is performed with a load equivalent to that of the digitizer. The resulting standard uncertainties are 0.2 % for amplitude and 0.2 crad for phase.
- Digitizer Calibration: As described earlier, the voltage ratio is calibrated using two known signals and FFT analysis. Given the scale factor of Path 2 (up to 3000), a harmonic at 0.01 % of a 5 V fundamental results in an up to 1.6 mV signal at the digitizer input. This can be easily acquired using the 10 mV range of the digitizer. The estimated standard uncertainty is 0.2 % for amplitude and 0.1 crad for phase.
- Filter Load Sensitivity: A 1 pF variation in capacitance and 1 % in the 1 MΩ resistive load introduce a phase uncertainty of approximately 0.04 crad and a gain uncertainty of about 0.9 % in the 9 kHz to 150 kHz frequency range.

3.4.5 Expanded uncertainties

The calibration uncertainty of the measurement chain was evaluated across the frequency range of 9 kHz to 150 kHz using the GUM. The results are summarized in Table 2 and Table 3, respectively, for amplitude and phase. The expanded uncertainties (with a coverage factor $k \approx 2$) were determined for different amplitude levels of harmonic components relative to the fundamental. Equation (4) has been used for the calculation of the expanded uncertainty.

$$U = 2 \sqrt{\sum u_i^2}, \quad (4)$$

where u_i is the standard uncertainty of each contribution source.

The results presented in Table 2 show that the measurement chain achieves expanded uncertainties close to the target values that we have fixed and required for the conformity assessment of IT instrument transformers according to IEC 61869 Class WB3. For the fundamental frequency, the uncertainty is slightly above the ideal target (0.028 % vs. 0.02 %) but remains acceptable for most practical applications. For harmonics with voltage output higher than 0.1 %; the uncertainties (0.29 % and 0.45 %, respectively) are also just above the target thresholds (0.2 % and 0.4 %) yet still demonstrate adequate performance for PQ evaluation in the 9 kHz to 150 kHz range. For very-low-level harmonics, 0.01 % of the fundamental, the expanded uncertainty reaches 2 %, which is two times higher than the fixed target uncertainty (1 % up to 150 kHz). The major contribution here is the load sensitivity of the filter.

Table 2. Calibration uncertainty of instrument transformers for amplitude

Contribution/Source	Fundamental (Path 1)	9 kHz to 150 kHz U out > 1 mV (Path 1)	9 kHz to 150 kHz U out < 1 mV (Path 2)
Calibration of path/HVD	0.0015 %	0.1 %	0.2 %
Digitizer calibration	0.01 %	0.1 % (U out > 10 mV) 0.3 % (U out > 1 mV)	0.2 %
Attenuator calibration	(included in path)	0.1 %	-
Load sensitivity	0.01 % (attenuator)	0.005 % (HVD) 0.03 % (attenuator)	0.9 % (filter)
Expanded uncertainty (k = 2)	0.028 %	0.29 % (U out > 10 mV.) 0.45 % (U out > 1 mV.)	1.9 %

Table 3. Calibration uncertainty of instrument transformers for phase

Contribution/Source	Fundamental (Path 1)	9 kHz to 150 kHz U out> 1 mV (Path 1)	9 kHz to 150 kHz U out< 1 mV (Path 2)
Calibration of path/HVD	0.0015 %	0.1 %	0.2 %
Calibration of path/HVD	0.0015 crad	0.1 crad	0.2 crad
Digitizer calibration	0.01 crad	0.1 crad	0.1 crad
Attenuator calibration	–(included in path)	0.1 crad	-
Load sensitivity	0.005 crad (attenuator)	0.005 % (HVD) 0.005 crad (attenuator)	0.04 crad (filter)
Expanded uncertainty (k = 2)	0.020 crad	0.3 crad	0.5 crad

3.5 Conclusion

A reference measurement chain for the assessment of medium-voltage instrument transformers ITs in the extended frequency range up to 150 kHz has been developed and validated. The chain is based on a dual-path architecture combining a wideband high-voltage divider, precision attenuators and a dedicated high-pass filter, enabling both accurate fundamental measurements and the detection of very-low-level harmonic components.

The results demonstrate that the chain achieves expanded uncertainties of 0.028 % at the fundamental frequency, below 0.5 % for harmonic components down to 1 mV (0.1 % of the fundamental) and around 1.9 % for very-low-level harmonics at lower than 1 mV (e.g. 0.01 % of the fundamental). Although these latter results remain compatible with the IEC 61869 Class WB3 requirements, the margin becomes narrow at such low levels. This limitation is mainly due to the sensitivity of the high-pass filter to load conditions and further improvements in the filter design are expected to reduce the uncertainty below the current 1.9 % and extend the chain to the WB4 range up to 500 kHz.

Finally, the chain described in this work can be reproduced by transformer manufacturers and adapted either for direct use in grid measurements under realistic conditions or for the characterization of their products in test laboratories. This makes it not only a reference for NMIs but also a practical tool for industry. This establishes the chain not only as a reference measurement setup but also as a high-voltage platform that can be reproduced and adapted for industrial applications.

4 RISE measuring system

4.1 Introduction

The objective of WP2 of the project was to design and characterise a voltage measurement system for measurements of line frequency and harmonics up to 5 kHz superimposed by supraharmonics in the frequency range 9 – 150 kHz. The measurement system shall meet the requirements for a substation monitoring with system voltage of 36 kV. A voltage divider thus have be designed for 21 kV phase-to-earth voltage.

RISE reference measurement system builds on the design of a 500/320 kV (DC/ACrms) universal divider which was developed in the EMPIR 19NRM07 HVcom2 project [1]. The divider was scaled down to a smaller broadband divider RCR125 - 125/80 kV (DC/ACrms), increasing the bandwidth from 500 kHz to 1 MHz to meet the frequency requirements of ADMIT. The RCR125 was designed, built and characterized late 2024, and the ratio and phase error is plotted in Figure 8.

Figure 8. The RCR125 divider and ratio/phase errors.

The performance of RCR125 was deemed insufficient and a decision was made to go beyond and reduce the ratio and phase errors further.

A new generation wideband divider, the RCR36, was designed and built to measure up to 50 kV DC, 36 kV ACrms, withstand 100/70 kV (DC/ACrms) and withstand 175 kV lightning impulse voltages. This divider has a crossover frequency of 3.8 MHz (C·Rd) and a crossover frequency L/Rd of 15 MHz.

Three RCR36 dividers are being built to be able to measure on three-phase systems. The digitizer for the final set-up is an 18-bit, 8ch simultaneously sampling board from National Instruments, the PXIe-6396. With this and three Rogowski current sensors a measurement system is ready to monitor power grids in substations with 36 kV system voltage. Here should be noted that the voltage divider will measure three phase voltages of 21 kV, and these must withstand overvoltages up to 70 kV [IEC 61869-1] which is met by this design.

An active bandpass filter with 10x or 100x amplification has been designed to increase the sensitivity for supraharmonics (9 – 150 kHz) with parallel sampling of the output from the divider. Each phase will then be simultaneously sampled by 2 channels.

4.2 The RCR36 system

A schematic of the system is shown in Figure 9 with divider, attenuator, bandpass amplifier and digitizer inputs per phase. A photo of the 3-phase voltage measurement system is presented in Figure 10 and builds on the experience of an earlier design [10]. For future use in substations the divider designed in this project must withstand 1.95 times the nominal phase voltage and if needed the HV modules can be stacked.

Figure 9. Schematic and physical layout of the measurement system.

Figure 10. Three phase voltage divider set-ups with PXIe-6396 digitizer.

The voltage divider has two outputs, one for DC and AC fundamental components, and the other for harmonics measurement. The harmonics measurement branch incorporates a precision voltage divider, filtering, and amplification before data acquisition. Filtering is necessary to attenuate the fundamental component, while the amplifier enhances the signal for precise measurement using the data acquisition system.

4.3 The divider

The voltage divider, with a nominal scale factor (SF) of 162, combined with an attenuator with SF 100, reduces the HV to measurable levels, lower than 2.0 V, 1.4 V, and 5.6 V for DC, AC, and impulse signals, respectively. The divider consists of HV/LV branches (1080 MΩ/6.7 MΩ) and a capacitive branch for AC measurements from 5 Hz to 1 MHz (300 pF/ 48 nF). The damping resistors (180 Ω/1.1 Ω) gives a crossover frequency from capacitive to resistive divider from damping resistors of 2.9 MHz and an upper bandwidth of c.a. 10 MHz from typical uncompensated inductance. The resulting modelled divider output is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Divider design (left) and modelled divider ratio and phase error (right).

The physical construction of the divider is compact (165 mm diameter, 250 mm high, weighs 6.7 kg) and optimized for HF response and low signal distortion. The system ensures accurate HV measurements across a broad frequency range (DC–150 kHz), making it suitable for harmonic analysis and HV testing while addressing key challenges such as low noise, electromagnetic interference (EMI) immunity, and stable frequency response.

4.3.1 The attenuator

The attenuator is also an RCR divider with SF 100, has a crossover frequency from capacitive to resistive divider from damping resistors and an upper bandwidth of 1.3 MHz, and an upper bandwidth of c.a. 74 MHz from typical uncompensated inductance. The measured ratio and phase error from characterization of an attenuator using RISE DSWM Ultra reference measurement system is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Measured attenuator ratio and phase error.

4.3.2 System performance

The resulting modelled system output is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Measured attenuator ratio and phase error.

4.3.3 Enhancement of the supraharmonics signals

Typically, the voltage levels of the supraharmonics are typically around 100 times lower than the line voltage levels. To measure those voltages in the 9 – 150 kHz range a bandpass amplifier has been designed, suppressing the line voltages and amplifying the supraharmonics. The first design amplifies the signals by a factor of 10. Design criteria for the bandpass amplifier are shown in Figure 14

Figure 14. Design of a bandpass amplifier.

4.4 Measurement uncertainties

Traceability of the measurement systems of RISE is ensured by the calibration of the divider together with the attenuator in a first step using the reference measurement system DSWM Ultra with a 1 MHz bandwidth. This procedure gives a ratio uncertainty up to 0.05% and a phase uncertainty of 0.02 mrad. The specified expanded measurement uncertainty from PXIe-6396 is better than 330 μ V/V for the 2 V range, which is the maximum output from the divider/attenuator. The digitizer measurement uncertainty therefore adds 0.033% for the ratio and a negligible contribution for phase error between channels from its simultaneous sampling.

The combined expanded uncertainty for the ratio is $\pm 0.06\%$ up to 150 kHz (DSWM). The combined uncertainty for phase displacement of the calibration set up is 0.02 mrad. Ratio errors and phase shifts in the bandpass amplifier will add to the uncertainty of the 9 – 150 kHz range is applied.

4.5 Conclusion

A three-phase measurement system for voltage measurements up to 36 kV AC rms and 50 kV DC has been designed and built for substation monitoring of line frequency, harmonics and supraharmonics voltages. These dividers together with current sensors will be offered as services for grid operators.

5 VTT measuring system

5.1 Low voltage multitone harmonics system

VTT system for generation and measurement of 50 Hz fundamental and harmonics is show in Figure 15. A signal with up to 10 frequency components is created, and it is uploaded to the two-channel arbitrary waveform generator (AWG, Keysight 33500B). One channel of the AWG feeds the voltage amplifier (Fluke 5205A), and the other channel provides a synchronized trigger signal to the two-channel digitizer (Applicos WFD20).

A wideband voltage divider is used as the reference for calibration of voltage sensors. The VTT low voltage reference voltage divider has been characterized up to 100 kHz using two methods, 1) by comparison with AC voltage reference (Fluke 5790), and 2) by calculation from step response. The voltage step was generated using a closing mercury-wetted relay switch. Comparison of the results obtained using the two method is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 15. VTT multitone generation and measurement setup.

f	Relative uncertainty
100 Hz	0.04 %
1 kHz	0.01 %
10 kHz	0.007 %
100 kHz	0.18 %

Figure 16. VTT low voltage reference divider amplitude response.

The system is controlled by a PC. A typical recorded reference multitone signal and its FTT are shown in Figure 17.

As the sampling is coherent with the multitone reference signal, no windowing is needed, and each generated harmonic will fall in one FTT bin without spectral leakage. Both gain error and phase displacement can be obtained by dividing the complex input Fourier spectrum of the device under calibration by the output spectrum.

Figure 17. An example of a measured multitone waveform. Even though the signal level is low, the signal-to-noise ratio is c. 75 dB.

5.2 High voltage multitone harmonics system

The VTT wideband high voltage divider was calibrated using the low voltage divider as reference. The amplitude response and phase displacement of the high voltage reference divider up to 100 kHz are shown in Figure 18. The amplitude response has been corrected according to low voltage divider response.

Figure 18. VTT high voltage reference divider amplitude and phase response.

5.3 Conclusion

A high-frequency reference measuring system has been validated to extend accurate medium-voltage instrument transformer and voltage sensor calibration for range from 10 Hz to 100 kHz. The system employs both low and high voltage wideband high-voltage RC dividers in combination with a high-resolution digital recorder.

Characterization tests have been performed to confirm the system's performance and identify key uncertainty influences. The high voltage reference system scale factor overall uncertainty up to 100 kV is less than 0.1 % from 50 Hz to 100 kHz, and the phase displacement uncertainty is less than 20 mrad in the same frequency range.

6 INRIM measuring system

6.1 Introduction

This section presents the reference dividers and the acquisition system adopted at INRIM for the characterization of MV transducers up to 150 kHz. They are integrated into a novel generation and measurement setup designed primarily for industrial applications and described in [6].

6.2 Description and Characterization

Measuring voltage system used at INRIM is based on the use of off-shelf resistive-capacitive voltage dividers (RCVDs) and an acquisition system. Two different RCVDs are available. First, indicated as RCVD_A is air insulated, designed for DC and AC (50/60 Hz) applications. It has a rated primary voltage of 3 kV, a rated scale factor (SF) equal to 1000 V/V and accuracy class of 0.2 %. The second RCVD (RCVD_B) is gas-insulated, and it designed for PQ applications, it has ± 45 kV rated primary voltage, a SF of 10000 V/V, a declared bandwidth from DC to 1 MHz and 0.2 accuracy class at 50/60 Hz.

The two RCVDs have been characterized with a sinusoidal frequency sweep (SFS) in the range [10; 150] kHz at reduced amplitudes using a Fluke 5730A calibrator and results are provided in Figure 19. As can be observed, RCVD_A SF variation is within 0.2 % whereas for RCVD_B it is within 0.5 %.

Figure 19. Frequency dependence of the two voltage dividers used in INRIM measuring system.

The measured reference and the test signals are acquired by a comparator that includes a NI compact Data Acquisition system (cDAQ) with the NI 9223 board. The module provides four simultaneously sampled differential input channels with a 16-bit resolution, enabling accurate measurement of fast-changing signals. Each channel supports a maximum sampling rate of 1 MHz, ensuring precise time alignment across all inputs. The input range is ± 10 V, with selectable AC or DC coupling. The module features an input impedance of 1 M Ω in parallel with approximately 100 pF and includes built-in anti-aliasing filters that automatically adjust according to the selected sampling rate. The analogue bandwidth is approximately 800 kHz, making the device suitable for high-frequency measurements.

The acquisition module NI 9223 was characterized in comparator mode, i.e., by providing the same signal to two channels. When used in this configuration, the frequency response in the [10; 150] kHz range is flat within ± 70 μ V/V.

6.3 Conclusion

This section has presented the reference dividers and the acquisition system adopted at INRIM for the characterization of MV transducers up to 150 kHz. They are integrated into a novel generation and measurement setup designed primarily for industrial applications and described in [6]. Both the transducers and the acquisition system are implemented using off-the-shelf instrumentation, which has been metrologically characterized at INRIM.

The maximum uncertainty obtained with the proposed setup in the frequency range from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz is lower than 1.5 % and 1.5 crad (95 % level of confidence) for the ratio and phase errors, respectively.

7 FFII measuring system

The reference measuring system to measure harmonics is composed of a high-voltage voltage divider developed in the HVcom² project and a high-resolution PicoScope 5400 digital recorder. Its characteristics, the characterization tests carried out, and the detailed estimation of the associated measurement uncertainties are described in the following paragraphs, focusing on the harmonic range of 9 kHz to 150 kHz.

7.1 Description of the Reference Measuring System

FFII measuring system is shown in Figure 20. The HVcom² voltage divider is a wideband high-voltage RC divider with a nominal ratio of approximately 1000:1. It was selected as the main divider for the reference measuring system because its transfer behaviour is designed to be relatively flat and stable in both amplitude and phase up to 150 kHz, while scaling the primary voltage down to levels compatible with the acquisition instrument.

The divider output is acquired using a PicoScope 5400 series digital recorder, which acts as the digitizer of the reference chain. The instrument provides high-resolution waveform capture up to 15 bits and a sampling capability sufficient to support harmonic analysis up to 150 kHz. Using two simultaneously sampled channels, it enables synchronous acquisition of the relevant low-voltage signals so that RMS values and spectral components can be computed through dedicated post-processing.

Figure 20. FFII Reference Measuring System.

7.2 Characterization Tests

A series of metrological tests were carried out on the complete measuring system to quantify each source of potential error. The main tests, the methodology followed and the most relevant results are described below:

7.2.1 Frequency response

The measuring system is subjected to a frequency response characterization to obtain the ratio and the phase shift error dependent with frequency from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. The voltage is generated by a wideband power amplifier and a step-up transformer, capable of generating sinusoidal RMS voltages up to 500 V.

For the output ratio, the divider's output was measured using the PicoScope 5400 series digital recorder and compared against a reference digital multimeter. For the phase shift error, the divider's output was measured using one channel of the Yokogawa WT5000 power analyser and compared against the other channel of the same instrument. Figure 21 and Figure 22 show the results of this characterization.

Figure 21. FFII reference measuring system output ratio frequency response.

Figure 22. FFII reference measuring system phase shift frequency response.

7.2.2 Short-Term Stability. Self-heating under DC stress

As an RC divider, it was observed that the resistances used for DC measurement would heat when subjected to DC application to verify that DC electrical stress and the associated self-heating do not modify the AC divider ratio. This test assessed the short-term stability of measuring system after prolonged DC energisation.

Two identical dividers were used. One divider was energised at 35 kV DC for 60 minutes and treated as the unit under test. The second divider was kept unenergised at ambient temperature and used as a reference. After 60 minutes, the DC source was removed, and a comparison measurement was performed between the heated divider and the reference divider by applying 500V RMS harmonics from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. Results are shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23. Output ratio changes due to self-heating.

7.2.3 Influence of High-Voltage conductor length

This test assessed the influence of the length of the high-voltage connection from the reference measuring system to the instrument under calibration. For this purpose, two identical dividers were energized in parallel. One divider was always connected in the same position, while the conductor length between dividers was increased from 0.3 m up to 3 m, separating the second divider from the reference divider. The outputs of both dividers were acquired simultaneously and compared to account for this effect. Results are shown in Figure 24.

The long lead introduced a small systematic under-reading with respect to the short-lead connection. Up to 100 kHz, the observed difference remained approximately 0.15 %. At 150 kHz, the deviation increased and reached about 0.4 %, with the divider connected through the 3 m lead reading lower. These results show that the high-voltage lead length can contribute a non-negligible error at the upper end of the frequency range and should be kept as short and as consistent as possible between reference and device under test during measurements up to 150 kHz.

Figure 24. Output ratio changes due to conductor between dividers length.

7.2.4 Influence of proximity of grounded structures

This test assessed whether nearby grounded structures influence the reference divider ratio through stray capacitance and electric field coupling. The divider was first measured in an open arrangement, with no large conductive objects close to it. A second configuration was then prepared by placing a grounded metallic plate at approximately 0.35 m from the divider. The same input voltages were applied in both configurations, and the divider output was compared against a reference multimeter. Results are shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25. Output ratio changes due grounded structures at 0.35 meters from the reference divider.

No measurable influence was observed. The divider output ratio remained the same, within the measurement uncertainty, when the grounded plate was introduced in the setup.

7.3 Estimation of Measurement Uncertainties

The main Type B uncertainty contributions for the measurement of the fundamental are as follows:

- **uB1, Certified reference ratio.** Uncertainty associated with the frequency response measurement to determine the ratio at different frequencies.
- **uB2, Reference Linearity with Voltage.** Possible variations of the reference divider scale factor with applied voltage level. Experimental tests showed that this effect is negligible for voltages from 300 V_{RMS} to 500 V_{RMS}.
- **uB3, Short term stability.** Possible variations of the reference divider scale factor due to thermal effects during prolonged DC stress. Experimental tests showed that this effect is negligible.
- **uB4, Long term stability.** Possible variations of the reference divider scale factor due to long-term drift between calibrations. No drift was observed in different experimental tests performed at different years during the during the project.
- **uB5, Measuring instrument resolution and processing software.** Includes uncertainties from the measuring instrument resolution and processing software and algorithms.
- **uB6, High voltage lead length.** Possible variations of the Represents the effect of HV cable length on measured voltage, due to additional inductance and capacitance. It is mainly relevant at the highest frequencies (≥ 100 kHz).

- **uB7, Impedance mismatch.** Possible variations of the reference digitizer input impedance, with respect to the DUT's own digitizer.

Table 4 and Table 5 summarize the uncertainty values, respectively, for amplitude and phase for 9 kHz and 150 kHz. The expanded uncertainties with a coverage factor $k = 2$ are also determined following equation (4).

Table 4. Calibration uncertainty of instrument transformers for amplitude

Contribution/Source	9 kHz Uncertainty contribution (%)	150 kHz Uncertainty contribution (%)
Certified Reference Ratio	0.05 %	0.23 %
Short Term Stability	0.005 %	0.005 %
Long Term Stability	0.005 %	0.005 %
Instrument resolution and software	0.006 %	0.006 %
High Voltage Lead Length	0.008 %	0.04 %
Impedance mismatch	0.006 %	0.006 %
Expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$)	0.1 %	0.5 %

Table 5. Calibration uncertainty of instrument transformers for phase

Contribution/Source	9 kHz Uncertainty contribution (crad)	150 kHz Uncertainty contribution (crad)
Certified Reference Ratio	0.15 crad	0.30 crad
Short Term Stability	0.02 crad	0.07 crad
Long Term Stability	0.02 crad	0.02 crad
Instrument resolution and software	0.06 crad	0.06 crad
High Voltage Lead Length	0.09 crad	0.60 crad
Proximity effect	0.02 crad	0.02 crad
Impedance mismatch	0.15 crad	0.15 crad
Expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$)	0.26 crad	0.8 crad

7.4 Conclusion

A high-frequency reference measuring system has been validated to extend accurate medium-voltage instrument transformer calibration into the supraharmmonic range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. The system employs a wideband high-voltage RC divider in combination with a high-resolution digital recorder.

Characterization tests have been performed to confirm the system's performance and identify key uncertainty influences. The complete reference system achieves expanded uncertainties ($k=2$) on the order of 0.1% (amplitude) and 0.26 crad (phase) at 9 kHz, increasing to approximately 0.5% and 0.8 crad at 150 kHz.

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8 UniCampania High Frequency Reference Device

8.1 Introduction

This section describes the design, the realization and the characterization of the High Frequency Reference Device (HFRD), used as the voltage reference in the setup for the characterization of VTs realized at UniCampania and described in the deliverable D3. More details about this topic can be found in the paper [6]

8.2 HFRD design

A novel reference device (HFRD) was specifically developed for the characterization of VTs in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz when also a MV tone at the 50 Hz is included into the test waveform. Currently, some NMIs offer calibration services of voltage measuring devices in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz, but they are limited to voltage levels up to 100 V and make use of only sinewaves. To overcome this limitation, the proposed HFRD has a high-pass filtering behaviour, with a cutoff frequency of 5 kHz in order to attenuate in a significant way the amplitude of the 50 Hz component at MV level. Additionally, HFRD has to exhibit a quite flat response in the [9, 150] kHz range with a proper Scale Factor (SF) to ensure the reduction of tone amplitudes to levels compatible with the input stage of the acquisition system, typically within the range of ± 10 V. In the design of such a device, it is also necessary to consider the contribution of the impedance (typically a resistance in parallel with a capacitance) introduced by the input circuit of the acquisition system.

As a result, considering the resistances and the capacitances required to implement HFRD, those introduced by the acquisition system and the capacitance introduced in parallel to the step-up transformer, a device with a bandpass behaviour is obtained.

The simplified circuit diagram of HFRD is provided in Figure 26, where also the generation section is reported. In particular:

- C_s is the capacitance parallel connected to the SUT, [11];
- C_f is the HFRD capacitance,
- R_1 and R_2 are the two resistances implementing the resistive part of the HFRD filter and, at the same time, the resistive voltage divider with a fixed SF;
- C_d and R_d represent the input capacitance and resistance of the acquisition system.

Figure 26. Simplified circuit diagram of the proposed generation and measurement setup.

In the case under analysis, R_d exceeds 100 G Ω , and thus it can be neglected, C_d is about 400 pF (including also the capacitance of the connection box and of the cable that connects it to the board) and R_1 is selected almost equal to 76 times R_2 to achieve a SF equal to about 77 V/V. By defining R_{tot} as the series of R_1 and R_2 and C_{tot} as the series of C_s and C_f , the transfer function of HFRD can be written as:

$$W(s) = \frac{sR_2C_sC_f(1/C_f + C_s)}{(1 + sR_{tot}C_{tot} + sR_2C_d + s^2R_1R_2C_{tot}C_d)} \quad (5)$$

This transfer function is characterized by one zero in $s = 0$ and, by approximating $R_{tot} \approx R_1$, two poles, having the associated time constants equal to $\tau_{p,1} = R_{tot}C_{tot}$ and $\tau_{p,2} = R_2C_d$.

Considering that the value of C_d is fixed and it depends on the acquisition system and that the value of C_s is set to meet the generation system requirements, C_f , R_1 and R_2 represent the only quantities that can be suitably selected to meet the design requirements. In this specific case, they are chosen as reported in Table 6, where also the cutoff frequency and the bandpass gain are provided.

Table 6. Reference filter parameters

Parameter	Value
C_F	275 pF
Maximum capacitor voltage	4 kV (AC voltage)
R_1	114.3 k Ω
R_2	1.5 k Ω
Bandpass gain	$\approx 1/80$
f_{cutoff}	≈ 5 kHz

8.2.1 Linear and non-linear parasitic effects of HFRD components

The resistors and the capacitors of HFRD can present linear and non-linear parasitic effects. For instance, the capacitive coupling (in the air) of the resistor terminals or the linear losses inside the capacitors can be considered linear effects; instead, the dependences of the resistance and of the capacitance on the amplitude of the applied voltages can be considered non-linear effects. Therefore, before the realization of HFRD, every single component was subjected to various kind of tests in order to quantify these effects.

The linear effects were quantified by analysing every single component through the Agilent (now Keysight) E4980A precision LCR meter, from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz. It was found that the best model for the resistors is a parallel connection of a resistance and of a capacitance; the parasitic capacitances are in the order ~ 100 fF for resistances in the order ~ 1 k Ω and ~ 10 k Ω . Instead, the best model for the capacitors is a series connection of a resistance and of a capacitance; the parasitic resistances are in the order ~ 0.1 Ω for capacitances in the order ~ 100 pF. Obviously, the presence of such linear parasitic effects alters the frequency behaviour of the components, making Figure 26 and equation (5) be only approximated versions of, respectively, the circuit diagram and the transfer function of HFRD. However, the circuit diagram shown in Figure 26 was numerically simulated, as it is and by including the measured linear parasitic effects. The maximum deviation between the magnitudes of the two simulated frequency responses was found lower than 0.25 %. For this reason, in order to not confuse the reader, Figure 26 and equation (5) do not include the linear parasitic effects. It is worth to underline that this decision does not affect the accuracy of the results shown in the rest of the paper, that remain rigorous. In fact, although Figure 26 and equation (5) neglect these effects, they are present in the physical realization of HFRD; thus, they are included in the frequency behaviour measured in Section 9.3 and treated as systematic effects, with the related measurement uncertainty, in the tests shown in Section 9.4. As regards the possible temperature dependence of resistors and capacitors, the used laboratory has a temperature control system. Therefore, no temperature-dependent variations are expected.

For what concerns the non-linear parasitic effects of both resistors as well capacitors, they are linked to the slight non-linear behaviour of the dielectric materials used for the internal insulation of the capacitors and as covers for the resistors. For the case at hand, the electrical properties of the dielectric material mainly depend on the RMS amplitude of the electric field inside the material, that is on the RMS amplitude of the voltage applied to the component (i.e. the resistor or the capacitor).

Since the modelling of non-linear phenomena inside the electric components, like resistors and capacitors, is not the focus of the paper, these phenomena are not considered in Figure 26 and equation (5). Instead, the impact of these effects on the HFRD performance and the associated uncertainty are accurately evaluated from an experimental point of view and the obtained results are discussed in Section 8.3.

8.3 HFRD characterization

The metrological characterization of the proposed device (HFRD) should be performed in the real operating conditions, that is with waveforms composed by a 50 Hz tone at MV level and one or more frequency components, with lower amplitude, in the range of [9, 150] kHz. However, this implies the necessity to have a reference device, to determine the metrological performance of HFRD. As highlighted in Section 8.2, currently,

to the best of the authors' knowledge, such a reference device is not available on the market nor at NMI level. This is why HFRD was developed.

Therefore, since in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz reference measurement instrumentation and procedures are available up to 100 V, the frequency behaviour of the proposed device has been measured at low voltage level. Some physical considerations can be made to justify this approach. HFRD is a passive device, made exclusively with resistors and capacitors, that have, at least nominally, a linear behaviour. Moreover, no resins or other insulation materials, with a possible non-linear behaviour, were used in the realization of HFRD. In addition, due to its high-pass frequency behaviour, the 50 Hz component at MV level is strongly attenuated; it mostly drops across the input capacitor of HFRD and just a residual part drops across the output resistive divider. It follows that: HFRD resistors always work at voltage levels in the order of tens of volt and their dissipated power at the maximum voltage is just a little fraction (lower than 0.1 %) of their power ratings.

Regarding the linear parasitic effects (see Section 8.2), since they do not depend on the applied voltage, their presence is accurately accounted when the HFRD frequency behaviour is measured at low voltage.

Following these considerations, the HFRD frequency behaviour has been measured at 7 V in the range [9, 150] kHz. Then, in order to consider possible dependency from the amplitude level, the ratio and phase errors at 50 Hz were measured at various amplitudes. Similar procedures, up to about 10 kHz, are commonly used by NMIs [12], [13]. The non-linear parasitic effects (Section 8.2) are instead accounted by executing specific tests on every single HFRD component and included in the uncertainty budget.

The measurement results are obtained by performing a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) over 10 cycles of the fundamental component as suggested by the International Standards [7, 8]. For each measurement, 31 iterations have been performed to evaluate the repeatability and stability according to GUM [9].

The SF and the phase error of HFRD are obtained as in equations (6) and (7):

$$SF_R(f) = \frac{V_p(f)}{V_s(f)} \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta\varphi_R(f) = \varphi_s(f) - \varphi_p(f) \quad (7)$$

where:

- $V_p(f)$ and $V_s(f)$ are the RMS values of the primary and secondary voltages at frequency f .
- $\varphi_p(f)$ and $\varphi_s(f)$ are the phase angles of the primary and secondary voltages at frequency f .

8.3.1 Low-voltage frequency characterization

In this test, HFRD was supplied directly by AWG1 and two DAQ channels are used to acquire the outputs of AWG1 and of HFRD. Figure 27 shows the measured SF (phase error) of HFRD in the range [50 Hz, 150 kHz], obtained by means of a frequency sweep with sinusoidal waveforms, having amplitude of 7 V, and according to equations (6) and (7). The initial high-pass behaviour, with a cut-off frequency of about 5 kHz, is clearly visible. Focusing on the high-frequency range, a low-pass trend, due to the parallel input capacitance of the comparator, that follows the nominal high-pass behaviour and becomes effective from about 50 kHz, can be observed. Indeed, the insets in Figure 27 show that, for frequency range from 50 kHz up to 150 kHz, the SF slightly raises, and the phase error drops below zero.

The uncertainties associated with SF_R ($\Delta\varphi_R$) have two contributions: the ratio (phase) error between the two DAQ channels (evaluated through a type B approach [9]) and the repeatability and stability (evaluated through a type A approach [9]). Nevertheless, the contribution due to DAQ channels is negligible with respect to the other contribution, especially at high frequency.

Figure 27. Frequency behaviour of SF (a) and phase error (b) of HFRD

Voltage dependence at power frequency

As described in Section 8.2, due to the possible voltage dependence of HFRD capacitor, possible deviations of HFRD behaviour, when it is used with an input voltage in the MV range rather than in the LV range, can occur. Therefore, in order to account for these possible deviations, HFRD has been tested at 50 Hz with increasing amplitudes from 10 % to 120 % of the rated voltage of the generation system. In this test, done at 50 Hz, LFRD was used as reference device.

Figure 28 shows the SF and the phase error deviations, at fundamental frequency and at different voltage amplitudes, with respect to the values obtained in the low voltage frequency characterization. It can be observed that the SF (phase error) deviation is lower than 0.05 % (within 0.8 mrad). These deviations of SF and phase error are included in the uncertainty associated to HFRD.

Figure 28. SF and phase error deviation, with respect to the value measured at 7 V, at fundamental frequency versus the percentage of rated setup voltage.

Impact of non-linear parasitic effects of HFRD resistors and capacitors

In this Section, results related to the quantification of non-linear parasitic effects of one single resistor and one single capacitor of HFRD are shown; similar results are obtained for all the other components.

As for the capacitor (C_{UT}), having a maximum applicable voltage of 700 V, the comparison method was used, like the one shown in [14], [15]. A reference capacitor (C_{REF}), calibrated at INRIM, having a maximum applicable voltage of 34 kV is used. The same voltage is applied to C_{UT} and C_{REF} ; their currents are measured through two 8.5 digit Digital MultiMeters Fluke 8508, calibrated at INRIM. Since the applied voltages are the same, the

ratio of the measured currents depends on the ratio of the capacitances. From the knowledge of the voltage dependence of C_{REF} (measured at INRIM), the voltage dependence of C_{UT} is measured.

Various waveforms are used:

- 1) a 50 Hz sinewave with amplitude from 100 V to 700 V;
- 2) a waveform with a fixed amplitude of 600 V composed by a 50 Hz fundamental tone and a 150 Hz and 30 % harmonic tone with variable phase;
- 3) a waveform with amplitude from 100 V to 700 V composed by a 50 Hz fundamental tone, a 10 kHz and 2 % tone, a 50 kHz and 1.2 % tone and a 150 kHz and 1 % tone.

It is worth to underline that the used waveforms represent realistic power system waveforms, and a wide variety of waveform amplitudes and shapes are involved. The maximum measured variation of C_{UT} in all the tests is lower than 0.031 %.

As regards the resistor (R_{UT}), subjected to a maximum voltage of 20 V (when 3.6 kV is applied to HFRD), the resistance was measured by using two 8.5-digit Fluke 8508 digital multimeters, one as voltmeter and one as ammeter. Various waveforms are used:

- 1) a 50 Hz sinewave;
- 2) a 10 kHz sinewave;
- 3) a 150 kHz sinewave;
- 4) a waveform composed by a 50 Hz tone, a 10 kHz and 2 % tone, a 50 kHz and 1.2 % tone, a 150 kHz and 1 % tone.

The RMS amplitudes are in the range [1, 20] V.

The maximum measured variation of R_{UT} in all the tests is lower than 0.032 %. These effects are treated as an uncertainty source and included in the uncertainty of \dot{G}_{HFRD} .

Uncertainty associated to HFRD

Four uncertainty sources have been identified for HFRD SF and phase error: 1) the contribution of DAQ channels (coming from INRIM calibration), 2) variation of the frequency behaviour with the input voltage amplitude, 3) the contribution of the non-linear parasitic effects of HFRD resistors and capacitors and 4) a contribution associated to repeatability and stability (evaluated through a type A approach 9). The DAQ contribution is negligible compared to the other three. As regards the input voltage contribution, it is evaluated by accounting the maximum SF and phase error deviations (see Figure 22). Similarly, the contribution of the non-linear parasitic effects is evaluated by accounting the deviations presented in previous section. The combined standard uncertainty on HFRD SF (phase error) goes from 600 $\mu\text{V/V}$ (630 μrad) at 9 kHz to 7.0 mV/V (6 mrad) at 150 kHz.

8.4 Frequency behaviour of a VT: measurement model and associated uncertainty budget

This section discusses the measurement model and the associated uncertainty related to the evaluation of the frequency behaviour of a VT. Referring to the measurement architecture of Figure 29, it is possible to express the complex gains of a DUT at fundamental frequency ($\dot{G}_{DUT,LF}$) and at high frequency ($\dot{G}_{DUT,HF}$), respectively, as in equations (8) and (9):

$$\dot{G}_{DUT,LF} = \frac{\bar{V}_{ch3} \dot{G}_{LFRD}}{\bar{V}_{ch1} \dot{G}_{LVD}} \dot{K}_{acq,31} \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{G}_{DUT,HF} = \frac{\bar{V}_{ch3} \dot{G}_{HFRD}}{\bar{V}_{ch2} \dot{G}_{LVD}} \dot{K}_{acq,32} \quad (9)$$

where:

- \vec{V}_{chX} is the phasor of the voltage acquired by the channel X of the DAQ;
- \hat{G}_{LFRD} is the complex gain of LFRD;
- \hat{G}_{HFRD} is the complex gain of HFRD obtained combining (3) and (4), $\hat{G}_{HFRD} = \frac{1}{SF_R} e^{j\Delta\phi_R}$.
- \hat{G}_{LVD} is the complex gain of the LVD (it is present only in the case of inductive VTs or for any DUT with voltage output greater than the maximum input voltage of DAQ);
- $\hat{K}_{acq,jk}$ is the complex ratio between the gain of DAQ channel j and the DAQ channel k.

Figure 29. Basic block scheme of the proposed generation and measurement setup arranged at University of Campania

All the complex gains of equations (8) and (9) represent systematic deviations that are evaluated and compensated. The values of \hat{G}_{LFRD} , \hat{G}_{LVD} and $\hat{K}_{acq,jk}$ and the associated uncertainties are obtained by the INRIM calibration (see Section III.A). The calibration of HFRD (\hat{G}_{HFRD}) has been previously discussed.

Table 7 reports, for each row, the uncertainty values, associated to a specific source, at various frequencies. Note that the contribution associated to \hat{G}_{LFRD} is present only in the first column because measurement model of equation (8) applies only at 50 Hz. Repeatability and stability (evaluated through a type A approach [9]) on the complex ratios $\vec{V}_{chj}/\vec{V}_{chk}$ are also reported.

Table 7. Uncertainty budget of $u_\epsilon(\mu V/V)$ and $u_{\Delta\phi}(\mu rad)$

Source	Frequency (kHz)									
	0.05		9		50		100		150	
	u_ϵ ($\mu V/V$)	$u_{\Delta\phi}$ (μrad)	u_ϵ ($\mu V/V$)	$u_{\Delta\phi}$ (μrad)	u_ϵ ($\mu V/V$)	$u_{\Delta\phi}$ (μrad)	u_ϵ ($\mu V/V$)	$u_{\Delta\phi}$ (μrad)	u_ϵ ($\mu V/V$)	$u_{\Delta\phi}$ (μrad)
\hat{G}_{LFRD}	50	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
\hat{G}_{HFRD}	-	-	600	630	1500	2100	5000	4000	7000	6000
\hat{G}_{LVD}	50	50	200	150	350	150	1300	350	1000	350
$\hat{K}_{acq,jk}$	40	40	40	40	120	120	400	400	400	400
Repeatability and Stability	10	10	30	50	60	150	100	300	200	300
u_c	82	82	630	650	1600	2100	5200	4000	7100	6000
U_c (95 %)	160	160	1300	1300	3200	4200	10000	8000	14000	12000

The last two rows of Table 7 report, respectively, the combined standard (u_c) and the expanded (U_c , level of confidence 95 %) uncertainties associated to \hat{G}_{DUT} . It can be noted that, especially at the higher frequencies, \hat{G}_{HFRD} is the main source of uncertainty. This is due to the effect of parasitic parameters, which becomes relevant at higher frequency and worsens the measurement repeatability, increasing, in turn, the uncertainty.

8.5 Frequency characterization of commercial Voltage Transformers

As an application of the realized measurement setup, the frequency characterization of two commercial VTs, a LPVT and an inductive VT was performed. The VTs' main features are summarized in Table 8.

The ratio and the phase errors of the VTs under test are measured as in equations (10) and in (11), respectively:

$$\varepsilon(f) = \frac{k_r \cdot V_s(f)}{V_p(f)} - 1 \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta\varphi(f) = \varphi_s(f) - \varphi_p(f) \quad (11)$$

where $k_r = V_{p,r}/V_{s,r}$ is the rated transformation ratio ($V_{p,r}$ and $V_{s,r}$ are the rated primary and secondary voltages).

The generated test waveforms are of FH1 type [16] and composed by the fundamental tone at 50 Hz and 3 kV, one frequency tone having frequency in the range [9, 150] kHz and amplitude equal to 2 % of fundamental tone.

Table 8. Rated characteristics of the analyzed VTs

	Rated primary voltage (kV)	Rated secondary voltage (V)	Rated Burden (VA)	Accuracy class
LPVT	3	3	5	0.5
Inductive VT	3	100	20	0.5

8.5.1 Characterization of LPVT

The ratio and phase errors of the LPVT at 50 Hz are, respectively, 0.1 % and 600 μ rad. Figure 30 shows the ratio and phase errors in the range [9, 150] kHz. It can be observed that the ratio error is within 10 % up to 130 kHz and equal to 11 % at 150 kHz. The phase error is within 0.1 rad up to 150 kHz. With reference to the accuracy classes extensions defined in [10], regarding the ratio error it can be observed that the LPVT totally meets the requirements of WB1 and WB2, whereas it only partially satisfies the requirements of WB3 and completely misses the ones of WB4. As regards the phase error, the LPVT meets the requirements of all the accuracy class extension, as the phase error is within $5.0^\circ = 0.087$ rad up to 150 kHz.

Figure 30. Ratio and phase errors versus frequency for the LPVT

8.5.2 Characterization of inductive VT

The ratio and phase errors of the inductive VT at 50 Hz are, respectively, 0.05 % and 500 μ rad. Figure 31 shows the ratio and phase errors in the range [9, 150] kHz. It can be observed that the ratio error is within ± 20 % up to 50 kHz. A first resonance occurs at about 12 kHz, whereas a second resonance, having a lower entity, at about 60 kHz. The last observable resonance occurs over 150 kHz. The phase error is within ± 0.4 rad up to 150 kHz. With reference to the accuracy class extensions defined in [10], regarding the ratio error it can be observed that the inductive VT totally meets the requirements of WB1, whereas it completely misses the ones of WB2, WB3, and WB4. As regards the phase error, the inductive VT totally meets the requirements of WB1 and WB2, whereas it only partially satisfies the requirements of WB3 and WB4. The IEC 61869-1 ed.2 specifies that some extensions defined in [10] may not apply to some specific ITs. These results show that the extended accuracy class limit should not be applied to inductive VTs.

Figure 31. Ratio and phase errors versus frequency for the inductive VT

8.6 Conclusion

This Section has a voltage reference device realized and characterized at UniCampania. It is inserted in a novel generation and measurement setup for the frequency characterizations of MV VTs from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz. The proposed architecture represents an extension of the measurement setups commonly employed by NMIs to characterize VTs. The generation is obtained by a series connection between two generators, a high-frequency amplifier and a step-up transformer, used to generate the power frequency component at MV level. The measurement of the fundamental component and of the high frequency components are obtained through two different reference devices. A commercial divider is used as reference device for the measurement of the fundamental component. Instead, a new reference device, operating in the range [9, 150] kHz, is designed, realized and characterized. The maximum uncertainty obtained with the proposed setup in the frequency range from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz lower than 1.4 % and 1.2 crad (level of confidence 95 %) for the ratio and phase errors, respectively. In conclusion, the proposed generation and measurement setup allows for the characterization of inductive and low power VTs at power frequency and from 9 kHz to 150 kHz with waveforms having amplitudes at MV level.

9 General conclusion

This work has presented the design, development, and characterization of several complementary voltage measurement systems for superimposed frequency components on range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz for the testing of medium-voltage instrument transformers. Performance of the following systems were investigated:

- The newly developed system at LNE provides a validated reference measurement chain for medium-voltage instrument transformers up to 150 kHz. Based on a dual-path architecture combining a wideband high-voltage divider, precision attenuators and a high-pass filter, it enables accurate fundamental and harmonic measurements. The achieved expanded uncertainties are 0.028 % at the fundamental frequency, below 0.5 % for harmonics down to 1 mV, and about 1.9 % for harmonics below 1 mV, remaining compatible with IEC 61869 Class WB3 requirements. Further improvements to the high-pass filter are expected to reduce uncertainties and extend the frequency range toward WB4 up to 500 kHz. The proposed chain can also be reproduced by manufacturers and adapted for industrial measurements and laboratory characterization.
- RISE uses the DSWM Ultra system for characterisation and calibration of the new RCR36 divider up to 700 V_{rms} and 150 kHz. The system uses a two-channel NI PXIe-5922 for reference signal and the output from the RCR36 with attenuator. A software controls a Fluke 5700A calibrator to set reference frequency and amplitude. A Fluke 5205A amplifier boost the voltage up to 700 V_{rms} which feeds the HV terminal of the RCR36. The DSWM low voltage reference system gives an expanded measurement uncertainty of 0.03% for ratio and 0.4 mrad for phase displacement at 150 kHz and 700V. Calibration to nominal 21 kV and 36 kV is based on a reference system using a compressed gas capacitor. Harmonics up to 5 kHz is calibrated up to 2 kV feeding the step-up transformer with an arbitrary waveform power amplifier. The reference high voltage gas capacitor divider has an uncertainty less than 0.01% up to 300 kV. DC calibration up to 50 kV has an uncertainty of 0.0015 %.
- VTT uses a low voltage multitone system, where the generation and measurement of the test signal are phase locked. A signal with up to 10 frequency components is created and amplified. A two-channel precision wideband digitizer is used to measure both the input and output voltage of the voltage divider or VT under test. Two reference dividers have been characterized, one for lower voltages up 300 V, and another for higher voltages up to 100 kV. The high voltage reference system scale factor overall uncertainty up to 100 kV is less than 0.1 % from DC to over 100 kHz, and the phase displacement uncertainty is less than 20 mrad in the same frequency range.
- Measuring voltage system used at INRIM is based on the use of off-shelf resistive-capacitive voltage dividers (RCVDs) and an acquisition system. Two different RCVDs are available. First, indicated as RCVD_A is air insulated, designed for DC and AC (50/60 Hz) applications. It has a rated primary voltage of 3 kV, a rated scale factor (SF) equal to 1000 V/V and accuracy class of 0.2 %. The second RCVD (RCVD_B) is gas-insulated, and it designed for PQ applications, it has ± 45 kV rated primary voltage, a SF of 10000 V/V, a declared bandwidth from DC to 1 MHz and 0.2 accuracy class at 50/60 Hz.
- FFII reference measuring system to measure harmonics is composed of a high-voltage voltage divider developed in the HVcom² project and a high-resolution PicoScope 5400 digital recorder. The complete reference system achieves expanded uncertainties ($k=2$) on the order of 0.1% (amplitude) and 0.26 crad (phase) at 9 kHz, increasing to approximately 0.5% and 0.8 crad at 150 kHz.
- UniCampania reference device, operating in the range [9, 150] kHz, is designed, realized and characterized. The maximum uncertainty obtained with the proposed setup in the frequency range from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz lower than 1.4 % and 1.2 crad (level of confidence 95 %) for the ratio and phase errors, respectively. In conclusion, the proposed generation and measurement setup allows for the characterization of inductive and low power VTs at power frequency and from 9 kHz to 150 kHz with waveforms having amplitudes at MV level.

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